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OIKONET Digital platform

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Deliverable Administration and Summary

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Work Programme Description	<p>Integrating of the components of the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus (Workspaces, Case Repository, OIKOpedia) with the new tools (graph search, dashboard, external tools). The work to be done encompasses: creating a new web-based environment for the project; establishing new automatic protocols to register network participants; adapting interfaces to larger community of users; installing databases in servers; and maintaining contents updated throughout the project lifetime.</p> <p>The platform environments will provide information about the activities of the network, facilitating the participation of third-parties in the activities, fostering communication among network partners, collecting and systematizing the collective knowledge generated across the different subnetworks.</p> <p>The platform will be built in three cycles, starting with a base environment created to be operative in month 3 of the project. Progressively, the new functionalities will be added to the platform as they are being developed.</p>				
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Document history

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2	2015-04-07	Marta Salgado (LA SALLE)	Description of technical implementation of the platform
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4	2016-11-25	Leandro Madrazo (LA SALLE)	Upgrade with latest improvements; including of usability test in Appendices
5	2016-11-28	Lisa Kinnear (LA SALLE)	Final proof-reading

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the work done concerning the design and implementation of the OIKONET digital platform. The platform started to be created from scratch at the start of the project. Later, it has been developed in successive stages, adding new components as the project progressed. A usability test has been conducted in the second half of the project to verify the functionality of the platform. 34 users from 27 partner organizations have taken part in the test (see Appendices A and B). The feedback received from users has been taken into consideration to improve the platform functionalities and the usability of its different components. After analysing the results of the tests, a series of enhancements were introduced to the latest released of the web portal on March 10, 2016.

The digital platform is a key component of the OIKONET project. It is meant to foster the communication and the collaborative work among project partners and to disseminate the project activities beyond the consortium.

The OIKONET digital platform integrates the following components into a unified information system:

- **Web portal**, the public repository of activities and public outcomes (www.oikonet.org).
- **Graph**, a visual map of the interrelated project activities
- **Dashboard**, it provides quick access to the project activities and products, organized by categories
- **Blogs**, dedicated to report the activities related to specific events, such as workshops, conferences and participatory actions .
- **File sharing system**, it is the repository of files, documents, etc. exclusive to partners (see Deliverable 1.1)
- **Social web**, tools to disseminate the project activities in:
 - **Facebook** (<https://www.facebook.com/oikonet>)
 - **Google +** (<https://plus.google.com/communities/107770894835201140122>)
 - **Twitter** (<https://twitter.com/oikonetorg>)

The platform will remain operative after the end of the funded period. OIKONET partners see the platform as a key resource to support future research and teaching, to support networking and to keep track of activities of partners. Furthermore, partners intend to continue to use the OIKONET portal in the educational and research work.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 Purpose and target group

This report summarizes the work carried out in the development of the OIKONET digital platform (www.oikonet.org) during the first reporting period of the project. It presents an overall structure of the platform and its major components. The target groups are the project partners as well as external readers working in the design and development of information systems supported by semantic technologies to support the communication and collaboration within a community of users.

2.2 Contribution of partners

The conception, design, implementation and maintenance of the digital platform have been carried out by the research group ARC Engineering and Architecture La Salle (arc.salleurl.edu). The usability test has been prepared by Anna Picco-Schwendener (USI). It has been performed by the following partners:

- P1 LA SALLE- School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona, Spain
- P2 ETSA-UPV- School of Architecture of Valencia, Spain
- P3 FASTU- Faculty of Architecture, Slovak Technical University, Bratislava, Slovakia
- P4 KUL- Faculty of Architecture, KU Leuven, Gent/Brussels, Belgium
- P7 CHALMERS - University of Chalmers, Sweden
- P8 IHS- Institute for Housing and Urban Development Studies, The Netherlands
- P9 UTH- Department of Architecture - University of Thessaly, Volos, Greece
- P10 UKIM - Faculty of Architecture, University Ss. Cyril and Methodius, Macedonia
- P11 OAPPCR- Ordine degli Architetti, Pianificatori, Paesaggisti e Conservatori della provincia di Rimini, Italy
- P12 UL- Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia
- P13 AAU- Department of Architecture, Design and Media Technology, University of Aalborg, Denmark
- P14 RTU - Faculty of Architecture and Urban Planning at Riga Technical University, Latvia
- P15 UCY- Faculty of Architecture, University of Cyprus, Cyprus
- P16 UCLAN- Grenfell-Baines Institute of Architecture, University of Central Lancashire, UK
- P17 PFZ- Faculty of Law, University of Zagreb, Croatia
- P18 UGA- Institut d'Urbanisme de Grenoble, Université Grenoble Alpes, France
- P19 NOVA- Norwegian Social Research, Norway
- P22 POLIS- Polis University, Albania
- P23 HERISCAPE- Heriscape, Italy

- P24 BRATISLAVA- City of Bratislava, Slovakia
- P27 BUT- Faculty of Architecture - Bialystok University of Technology, Poland
- P28 ELTE- Faculty of Social SciencesEötvös Loránd University, Hungary
- P29 DIT- School of Architecture, Dublin Institute of Technology, Ireland
- P30 ITU- Faculty of Architecture, İstanbul Technical University, Turkey
- P31 VSUACE-Volgograd State University of Architecture and Civil Engineering, Russia
- P32 FAU- Facultad de Arquitectura y Urbanismo, Universidad de Chile, Chile
- P33 UPPR- School of Architecture, Polytechnic University of Puerto Rico

2.3 Relations to other activities in the project

All project activities are represented in the information structure of the digital platform. Partners and third-parties can easily find on the platform the outputs generated during the project (activities, reports, publications, events), in an easy and in a straightforward way. The platform will remain a key component of the dissemination strategy of the project results, and it will keep providing information about the future activities of the network.

3 PLATFORM DEVELOPMENT

3.1 Platform structure

The digital platform was already operative in month 18 of the project, well ahead the scheduled deadline (month 24). The structure of the platform and its components is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Structure of the OIKONET Digital Platform

- **Web portal**, it is the public repository of activities and public outcomes (www.oikonet.org).
 - **Graph**, associative search through the information generated by the network
 - **Dashboard**, it provides a quick access to the project activities and products, organized by categories
- **Blogs**, dedicated to report the activities related to specific events, such as workshops, conferences and participatory actions .
- **File sharing system**, it is the repository of files, documents, etc. exclusive to partners (<https://lasalleuniversities.sharepoint.com/sites/oikonet>).
- **Social web**, tools to disseminate the project activities in:
 - **Facebook** (<https://www.facebook.com/oikonet>)
 - **Google +** (<https://plus.google.com/communities/107770894835201140122>)
 - **Twitter** (<https://twitter.com/oikonetorg>)

In this deliverable, we mostly focused on the content of the web portal. The file sharing system is described in Deliverable 1.1. The graph and dashboard are reported in Deliverables 5.2 and 5.3, respectively. The social web components are presented in Deliverable 7.2.

3.2 Web portal

The web portal has been designed and implemented from scratch and it has been developed step-by-step as the project progressed. It fulfills two basic objectives:

- to facilitate continuous and updated information of the project activities to OIKONET partners as well as to external users
- to provide access to the public project outcomes – reports, deliverables, videos.

An early version of the web portal was launched in month 3 (Figures 2, 3). It contained the basic information about the project. In subsequent releases, new components were added – connections to social web, graph and dashboard. The feed-back and suggestions from OIKONET users were taken into account to improve the early version.

Figure 2. Early version of the project web portal (month 6 of the project)

Figure 3. Early version of the project web portal (month 6 of the project)

The version of the web portal and its structure, as implemented at the end of the first half of the project, is shown in Figure 4.

The screenshot shows the OIKONET web portal home page. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for Home, Project, Consortium, Partners, Conferences, Workshops, Activities, News, Outcomes, Meetings, Exhibitions, Learning spaces, Newsletters, and CONTACT. Below this is a main banner with the text "A global multidisciplinary network on housing research and learning." The main content area is a grid of project activities, each with a date, title, and a small image or video thumbnail. On the right side, there are several widgets: "Follow us" with social media icons, "Subscribe to our newsletter" with a form, "OIKONETWORK" with a description and a graph icon, "OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus" with a list of resources, "RECENT NEWS" with a list of news items, and "TWITTER" with a channel icon. Annotations in yellow boxes point to these various elements.

Figure 4. OIKONET web portal: Home page (table view)

3.2.1 Web portal contents

The contents of the portal are static (in pages such as Project, Consortium and Contact) and, mostly, dynamic (all other pages that obtain the data from the semantic data repository). The information has been dynamically modelled using the tools developed in the project, particularly the semantic data repository API tool see section 4.15 in Deliverable 5.2/5.3). Each information element on the web portal is related to other elements (for example, a “Workshop” is related to the partners who participated in, to the “News” which has been generated, to the “Exhibitions” which have been organized) that are relationally described in the information system by means of the graph tool (see Deliverable 5.2). This enables the easy retrieval of the information associated to an item selected in the main menu (for example, to see all the presentations delivered in a sub-network meeting).

In the version of the portal which was operative at the end of the first hal of the project, the contents of the portal were described according to the structure:

- **Home.** This is the portal home page, which provides easy access to the interlinked components. It is dynamically updated showing the latest activities. It displays the information in two ways: as a table and as a list (Figure 5).

Figure 5. OIKONET web portal: Home page (list view)

- **Project.** A concise description of the project objectives and the structure of the network (Figure 6).

Figure 6. OIKONET web portal: Project

- **Consortium.** Access to the web sites of each OIKONET partner (Figure 7).

Figure 7. OIKONET web portal: Consortium

- **Partners.** Short description of each partner and staff members involved. The related items provide information about the partner tasks as described in the work programme, and the outcomes produced (Figure 8).

Figure 8. OIKONET web portal: Partners

- **Conferences.** There is a submenu for each of the three scheduled conferences, in Barcelona, Bratislava and Preston (Figure 9). For each item in the submenu, there is a full description of the conference program and the associated outcomes (presentations, videos).

Figure 9. OIKONET web portal: Conferences

- **Workshops.** There is a submenu for each of the three international workshops planned in the project, in Lisbon, Cottbus and Belgrade (Figure 10). Each item in the submenu provides access to the workshop program and related items (participants, outcomes, blogs,...).

Figure 10. OIKONET web portal: Workshops

- **Activities.** They refer to the on-going work being done during the project (Figure 11), which cannot be classified under another category (e.g. log, meetings, learning spaces)

Figure 11. OIKONET web portal: Activities

- **News.** Project outcomes and activities which are relevant for dissemination within the consortium and to the outside (Figure 12). News are also distributed through the social web channels (e.g. Twitter). [This view was later removed in the next release of the web portal]

Figure 12. OIKONET web portal: News

- **Outcomes.** The products resulting from the project activities such as reports, deliverables and videos (Figure 13).

Figure 13. OIKONET web portal: Outcomes

- **Meetings.** The meetings carried out at the level of the subnetwork and project levels (Figure 14). [This view was moved under the category “Activities” in a later release]

Figure 14. OIKONET web portal: Meetings

- **Exhibitions.** Repository of the exhibitions done during the project (Figure 15). [This view was placed under “Dissemination” in a later release of the portal]

Figure 15. OIKONET web portal: Exhibitions

- **Learning spaces.** A summary of the collaborative learning spaces carried out in the project, with a direct access to the OIKODOMOS Workspaces used by each one (Figure 16). [This view was moved under the category “Activities” in a later release]

Figure 16. OIKONET web portal: Learning spaces

- **Newsletters.** A repository of the newsletters produced in the project (Figure 17). [This view was placed under “Dissemination” in a later release of the portal]

Figure 17. OIKONET web portal: Newsletters

- **Contact.** Emails to contact the project coordinator and the work package leaders (Figure 18).

Figure 18. OIKONET web portal: Contact

3.2.2 Web portal implementation

The OIKONET web portal has been implemented in PHP using the development framework CodeIgniter (www.codeigniter.com). The front-end interface has been implemented in HTML, CSS and Javascript.

The portal is composed of static pages such as Project, Consortium and Contact. Besides, the portal includes dynamic pages that get their content from the semantic data repository (see Deliverables 5.2 / 5.3) using the tools developed in this project, particularly the semantic data repository API tool (see section 4.15 Deliverables 5.2 / 5.3). The process for retrieving data from the semantic data repository is the following:

1. The web portal invokes a method of the API
2. The API retrieves the data from the semantic data repository
3. The API encapsulates the data in JSON format and sends back the data to the web portal
4. The web portal decodes the JSON data and renders in the front-end interface using HTML, CSS, and Javascript.

For example, to display the elements of a category (e.g. News), the method “sendFormInstances” from the semantic data repository API is invoked with the following parameters:

- Category of the element. For example: News.
- Number of elements to retrieve: 5 (The last five news will be retrieved).

The method “sendFormInstances” will return the elements in JSON format. For example, a JSON data which contains the last five news would be like this:

```
array(
  ['type'] => 'News'
  ['offset'] => 0
  ['limit'] => 5
  ['content'] => array(
    [0] => array(
      ['uriId'] => 565
      ['formType'] => 'News'
      ['title'] => array(... 2 elements ... )
      ['content'] => array(... 2 elements ... )
      ['date created'] => array(... 2 elements ... )
      ['creator'] => array(... 2 elements ... )
      ['DomainRelation'] => array(... 2 elements ... )
      ['label'] => array(... 2 elements ... )
    )
    [1] => array(... 9 elements ... )
    [2] => array(... 10 elements ... )
    [3] => array(... 8 elements ... )
    [4] => array(... 7 elements ... )
  )
  ['numInstances'] => 5
  ['numTotalInstances'] => 26
)
```

The JSON data contains an array with all the elements (e.g. News) and their attributes (e.g. title, content, date created). The web portal processes the JSON data and generates a view rendering the data in HTML elements.

This is another example to retrieve data from the semantic data repository. In this case the method “sendInstance” is invoked which requires only the identifier of the element. The response of the API semantic data repository is a JSON data with the following structure:

```
array(
  ['uriId'] => 472
  ['formType'] => 'Learning space'
  ['Title'] => array(... 2 elements ... )
  ['start date'] => array(... 2 elements ... )
  ['end date'] => array(... 2 elements ... )
  ['description'] =>array(... 2 elements ... )
  ['partners'] => array(... 2 elements ... )
  ['activity'] =>array(... 2 elements ... )
  ['DomainRelation'] =>array(... 2 elements ... )
  ['label'] =>array(... 2 elements ... )
)
```

In this case, the JSON dataset contains attributes from a “Learning space” element” such as the title, start date, description, partners involved, among others. The elements can be related to other elements. For example, the “Learning space” elements are related to “Activity” elements. The relations also are in the JSON dataset retrieved from the semantic data repository. For example, unfolding the array named “activity” of the previous example we can be observed that contains two activities:

```
['activity'] => array(
  ['objectType'] => 'multiRelations'
  ['content'] => array(
    [0] =>array(
      ['uriId'] =>540
      ['formType'] => 'Activity'
      ['title'] =>'Learning Space “Housing Regeneration Strategies”'
      ['content'] => ...
      ['date created'] => '29-01-2015'
      ['image']=>'http://www.oikonet.org/resource/formularyInstance/539'
      ['relations'] =>array(... 1 element ... )
      ['video']=>'http://www.oikonet.org/resource/formularyInstance/538'
      ['label'] =>'Learning Space “Housing Regeneration Strategies”'
    )
    [1] => array(
      ['uriId'] => 462
      ['formType'] => 'Activity'
      ['title'] => ...
      ['content'] => ...
      ['date created'] => '06-11-2014'
      ['image'] =>'http://www.oikonet.org/resource/formularyInstance/463'
      ['label'] => ...
    )
  )
)
```

Figure 19 shows the elements related to the selected category in a page of the web portal. The selected category is a learning space named “Habitat Regeneration Strategies” which is related to three other elements: activities, documents, and partners.

Figure 19. Contents dynamically generated from the semantic data repository, showing the relationships between the different elements of information

4 FURTHER ENHANCEMENTS

During the second half of the project, a usability test of the OIKONET platform was prepared by USI and then submitted to the partners. A total of 34 tests were completed from 27 partner institutions (see Appendices). After analyzing the outcomes of the tests, the platform development team carried out the following enhancements (Figures 20, 21):

- redesign of the header of the home page: including information about the purpose of the website
- redesign of menus and submenus: reducing the number of elements, making the menu hierarchy more understandable, making the two menus in the web portal and in Oikonetwork consistent
- redesign of the right-side menu: it behaves now as a menu.
- removing the News section on the right side: to avoid overlapping with other information in the home page, all news are displayed only in the Twitter channel.

Figure 20. Improvements in the home page

Figure 21. Simplified structure of menus and submenus

Besides, to help users to navigate in the web portal, two tutorials were created (Figure 22, 23):

- a helping guide in the home page: guidelines to access information in the web portal, and to continue the search in Oikonetwork

Figure 22. Guidelines to navigate in the web portal

- a tutorial for Oikotnetwork

Figure 23. Oikotnetwork tutorial

These enhancements were included in the last release launched on March 10, 2016

5 CONCLUSIONS

The development of the digital platform was completed during the first eighteen months of project activity. The design and implementation of the digital platform has been carried out from scratch. Starting with an early version released on month three of the project, the platform has been progressively developed. In parallel to this development, the information generated in the project has been structured, shared and disseminated through the different components of the platform (web portal, file sharing system, social web). The structure of the information has been redefined as the project activities were taking place.

Once the semantic repository became operative in month eight of the of the project, it was possible to insert the data that was being collected by other means (Google docs, Word and PDF documents, email communications) to create a consistent network of interrelated information which reflects the manifold interactions between partners and the work they are producing in the project.

In the second half of the project, a usability test has been performed by 34 users from 27 partner organizations. After analysing the results of the tests, a series of improvements were introduced in the latest version of the platform: the navigation structure was reorganized, the menus and submenus simplified, and the consistency between the navigation in the web portal and in Oikonetwork was improved.

The traffic analysis documented in Deliverable 6.4 “Evaluation of the digital environment” shows that the visits to the OIKONET website have become more regular in the second half of the project, as compared to the first half: there are no high peaks visible, but visits are more numerous and better distributed along the months. Also, a survey among partners concerning the future exploitation of the digital resources (see Deliverable 8.5 “Digital Resources”) suggests that the web portal has become a consolidated source of valuable information. In particular, partners see the OIKONET portal as a key resource to support future research and teaching. With this aim, partners intend to continue to use the OIKONET portal and to keep providing contents to it.

6 APPENDIX A – USABILITY TEST: PROCEDURES AND TASKS

A usability test was prepared by Anna-Picco Schwendener (USI) and then to partners for executing it at their institutions.

INTRODUCTION

Usability is here defined as “the effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction with which specified users can achieve specified goals in particular environments” (ISO 9241-11). In online environments, the main goal of a usability evaluation is to detect (some of) the problems and obstacles that hinder users in reaching their goals while interacting with the online application(s).

The usability analysis will be conducted through activities of **user testing**: users (in this case teachers and/or researchers in the field of Architecture or Urban Design) will be asked to perform some real tasks on the web applications, while an OIKONET project partner will act as expert/inspector monitoring them and evaluating if they can complete the assigned tasks in an easy way.

PROCEDURE

A teacher or researcher of an organization participating in the OIKONET project (**user tester**) performs the test under the guidance of a member of the OIKONET team (**inspector**).

If necessary, the inspector quickly introduces the OIKONET project, then s/he asks the user tester to perform the following tasks from the OIKONET web portal (www.oikonet.org):

- T1. To search info about the program of activities “Thinking dwelling”: which activities are being done in the program?
- T2. To search the term “Gentrification” in the OIKOPEDIA.
- T3. To search info about the outcomes of the participatory action in Rimini (video).
- T4. To search the description of the participatory action in Bratislava in the blog COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION.
- T5. To search the contact of the leader of Work Package 2.
- T6. To go to the OIKONET page in Facebook, and search info about the “Housing design” MOOC: is it still running? When will it finish? Can I enrol? (if s/he wants, s/he can put a Like on the page)
- T7. To search information about the Learning Space “Threshold Matters”: is it still active? Which are the partners involved?
- T8. To search the video of the keynote speech of Ekim Tan at the Barcelona conference.
- T9. To go to Oikonetwork.
- T10. To search in Oikonetwork the document presenting the international workshop that was held in Cottbus last June.
- T11. To search in Oikonetwork which News are related with Workpackage 2 “Housing research”.

- T12. To search in Oikonetwork information on the project's research activities about the issue of "Resettlement": who is working on it? Which other themes and subthemes are connected to it?
- T13. To go back to the OIKONET website and search the last issue of the newsletter (if s/he wants, s/he subscribe to the newsletter).

The inspector asks the user tester to **think aloud** while performing the tasks, i.e. to speak and make explicit what s/he is trying to do, what s/he is expecting to get while clicking on a link, and so on.

If necessary, while introducing a task the inspector gives short explanations about the project tools and resources (e.g., what is a Learning Space, what is the OIKOPEDIA, and so on).

The inspector observes the user tester while s/he performs the tasks. If necessary, the inspector can answer the questions of the user tester and give him/her some suggestions if s/he is not able to perform a task.

At the end of each task, i.e. when the user tester has accomplished it or renounced, the inspector quickly discusses with the user tester about his/her experience in performing the task, his/her satisfaction, possible problems that have arisen, and so on.

At the end of the whole procedure, the inspector shortly discusses with the user tester to wrap-up his/her general experience while navigating in the OIKONET digital environments, trying to address specifically the main questions about the usability dimensions (see below) that have not been addressed before.

REPORTING

The inspector annotates the results of each task in the **Usability Form**. For each task, the inspector should indicate:

1. **How long did it take**, until accomplishment or renounce? (in minutes)
2. **Did the user complete the task?** (yes | no)
3. **Was s/he satisfied overall?** (1=not at all, 5=completely)

Furthermore, the inspector articulates usability judgments, reporting the issues that emerged during the navigation around some basic usability dimensions:

- **Orientation**: does the user understand where s/he is, in what position s/he is in the application?
- **Navigation**: can the user easily reach the tool/page/content s/he is looking for? Can s/he identify the right path to it?
- **Predictability**: is the user able to know what is going to happen when s/he clicks on a link/button? Does s/he get surprises?
- **Layout**: is the layout consistent? Is the user able to identify functional areas that support easy interaction?
- **Legibility/Graphics**: can the user read the content? Are the graphic elements useful to work with the application or are they confusing?
- If possible, the inspector should also annotate specific difficulties or good things.

The whole process should take **about 45 minutes**.

7 APPENDIX B – RESULTS OF THE USABILITY TEST

The test was conducted from October to December 2015. 34 users from 27 partner organizations carried out the test. The outcomes of the tests led to the changes introduced in the latest release of the web portal, on March 10, 2016.

INTRODUCTION

Goal of the usability evaluation was to detect some of the possible problems and obstacles that may hinder visitors of the OIKONET web portal (www.oikonet.org) in achieving their goals.

The usability evaluation was made through activities of user testing: users (in this case teachers and/or researchers in the field of Architecture or Urban Design) were asked to perform some real tasks on the OIKONET web portal, while an OIKONET project partner acted as expert/inspector monitoring them and evaluating if they could complete the assigned tasks.

The evaluation team created 13 different tasks that could be accomplished on the OIKONET web portal. The 13 tasks were created in a way that most parts of the website had to be visited. Some tasks also involved the use / visit of secondary project webpages and social media pages. During the general meeting at the end of September 2015, the evaluation team presented the procedure for the usability test to all partners. The goal was that each partner would carry out at least one usability test with a colleague at his/her institution. A document with the procedure to follow and the presented tasks was distributed via e-mail to all partners (see Appendix 1).

Some general data were collected for each tester (age, technical skills, past experience with OIKONET portal and institution). The expert measured the time a tester took to accomplish a task. After each task the tester had to rate how satisfied s/he was with the accomplishment of the task (scale from 1- not at all to 5 – completely). The expert wrote down the issues and difficulties that emerged during the test and possible comments by the tester.

A total of 34 usability tests, from 27 different partner institutions have been carried out in this way, as reported in the following table:

Partner Institution	Number of tests	Partner Institution	Number of tests
P1-LA SALLE	3	P17-PFZ	1
P2-ETSA-UPB	1	P18-UGA	1
P3-FASTU	1	P19-NOVA	1
P4-KUL	1	P22-POLIS	1
P7-CHALMERS	1	P23-HERISCAPE	1
P8-IHS	1	P24-BRATISLAVA	1
P9-UTH	1	P27-BUT	3
P10-UKIM	1	P28-ELTE	1
P11-OAPPCR	1	P29-DIT	1
P12-UL	1	P30-ITU	1
P13-AAU	2	P31-VSUACE	2
P14-RTU	1	P32-FAU	1
P15-UCY	1	P33-UPPR	1
P16-UCLan	2		

Furthermore, the evaluation team carried out 5 usability tests using an eye-tracking tool: the users were asked to solve the same tasks as in the normal usability test, while a hardware was tracking their eye movements, allowing to understand which areas of the website were looked at mostly and where users were looking in order to find specific information to solve their tasks. After each task, the testers were asked how satisfied they were with the task (scale 1-5) and the expert annotated any issue that emerged. The expert did not interrupt the tester with questions. At the end of the test, in a “Retrospective Think Aloud” scenario, the five testers commented on their overall navigation experience.

It has to be considered that the later tasks might have been easier to be achieved than the first ones, thanks to the experience gained by the user from completing the previous tasks.

RESULTS BY TASKS

In this section, the results of the usability analysis are presented, divided per tasks. The following table gives an overview of the tasks, of their completion and of the users’ satisfaction in accomplishing them:

Task	Nr. Resp.	Not compl. / with help	Avg. Satisf.
T1: Search information about the program of activities “thinking dwelling”	39	2 / 1	3.62
T2: Search the term “Gentrification” in the “OIKOPEDIA”	39	1 / 1	3.26
T3: Search info about the outcomes of the participatory action in Rimini (specifically a Video)	39	5 / 0	3.36
T4: Search the description of the participatory action in Bratislava in the blog "Community Participation"	39	5 / 0	3.63
T5: Search the contact of the leader of WP2 (Housing Research)	39	5 / 3	3.54
T6: Go to the OIKONET Facebook page and search for infos about the "Housing design" MOOC: Is it still running? When will it finish? Can I still enroll?	33	17 / 1	2.03
T7: Search infos about the Learning Space "Threshold Matters": Is it still active? Which are the partners involved?	38	0 / 1	3.66
T8: Search the video of the keynote speech of Ekim Tan at the Barcelona conference	38	4 / 1	4.13
T9: Go to the Oikonetwork	38	2 / 0	4.55
T10: Within the Oikonetwork search the document presenting the international workshop held in Cottbus last June	37	2 / 1	3.76
T11: Within Oikonetwork look for the news related to WP2 (Housing Research)	37	1 / 1	3.30
T12: Within Oikonetwork look for information on research activities on "Resettlement": who is working on it? Which other themes / subthemes are connected to it?	38	2 / 0	3.42
T13: Go back to the OIKONET website and search the last issue of the newsletter & try to subscribe	37	0 / 0	4.62

T1: SEARCH INFORMATION ABOUT THE PROGRAM OF ACTIVITIES “THINKING DWELLING”

Note: at the end of September, when the question was presented to the testers, the “tile” with the information about "Thinking Dwelling" was in the 1st row, in the middle of the home screen and thus easily findable. Later on, especially when the eye-tracking tests were done (end of December), the square had moved down on the home screen and was only visible after scrolling. Finding this information elsewhere on the website, without knowing that it is stored under Learning Spaces, was nearly impossible for an outsider.

Average satisfaction: **3.62**

Respondents: 34 + 5 = **39**

Task **not** completed by: **2**

Task completed with help: **1**

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Project Activities

January 12, 2016

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December 17, 2015

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The first OIKONET conference was organized by La Salle School of Architecture in Barcelona, Spain, in September 2014, the second one by the Faculty of Architecture, Siles University of Technology in Bilbao, Spain, in September 2015. The next conference will showcase the results obtained in the three years of activity of OIKONET involving research, pedagogy and community participation around the topic "Global Dwelling". During this period OIKONET partners have been involved in the design and implementation of pedagogical and research activities which have brought together schools of architecture and planning, research groups, professional organizations and local administrations. This is reflected in the collaborative learning spaces and workshops, community-based projects and participatory actions carried

December 15, 2015

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OIKONET Blogs

- Barcelona International Conference
- Bratislava International Conference
- Community Participation
- Cottbus Workshop
- Housing Research Reader
- Lisbon Workshop

The screenshot displays the OIKONET Digital Platform homepage. It features several news articles and navigation menus. The main content area includes:

- Top Left Article:** A photograph of a city street with buildings. Text: "The meeting will be dedicated to present the collaborative learning activities carried out in the Winter semester, and to finalize the program of the third international Workshop to take place in Belgrade in June 2016. The agenda includes two working sessions to discuss the collaborative learning... [READ MORE](#)"
- Top Middle Article:** Text: "The third OIKONET conference on 'Global Dwelling' will be hosted by the Faculty of Architecture, School of Art, Design and Fashion, University of Central Lancashire." Below this, a smaller article: "The first OIKONET conference was organized by La Salle School of Architecture in Barcelona, Spain, in September 2014. The second one by the Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Slovakia, in September 2015. This third conference will be hosted in Manchester, UK." Logos for OIKONET, uclan, and other partners are shown.
- Top Right Article:** Text: "The fifth meeting of the subnetwork will take place at the MKC (Mladinski Kulturen Center) – NGO Center in Skopje." Includes social media icons for Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube.
- Middle Left Article:** Date: "September 09, 2015". Text: "Second International Conference in Bratislava coming soon." Includes a green graphic of a city skyline.
- Middle Middle Article:** Date: "July 28, 2015". Title: "THINKING DWELLING". Text: "THINKING DWELLING is a program of activities –on-line and face-to-face- designed to engage students and teachers from different courses, levels and schools, in a joint process of reflection about contemporary dwelling. The activities to be submitted on-line (by students and teachers)..." Includes social media icons.
- Middle Right Article:** Date: "November 18, 2015". Text: "The fifth meeting of the subnetwork 'Housing Research' will take place in Zagreb, on November 20, 2015." Includes the logo of the University of Zagreb (UNIVERSITAS STUDIORUM ZAGREBENSIS MDCLXIX).
- Bottom Middle Article:** Text: "The meeting will be hosted by Institute for Social Policy, University of Zagreb. It will be dedicated to review the research themes proposed by partners presented in the OIKOPEDIA knowledge base and in the..." Includes social media icons.
- Right Side Navigation:**
 - OIKONET Blogs:**
 - Barcelona International Conference
 - Bratislava International Conference
 - Community Participation
 - Cottbus Workshop
 - Housing Research Reader
 - Lisbon Workshop
 - Manchester International Conference
 - OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus:**
 - Workspaces
 - Case repository
 - Oikopedia
 - RECENT NEWS:**
 - December 19, 2015** The fifth meeting of the subnetwork "Community Participation" is hosted by the Department of Architecture of the Sts. Cyril and Methodius University, in Skopje.
 - December 17, 2015** The third OIKONET International Conference on Global Dwelling has been announced. The conference will take place in Manchester, on...
 - November 20, 2015** The fifth meeting of the subnetwork "Housing Research" takes place in Zagreb. The meeting is hosted by the Faculty of Law, Department of Social Work, University of Zagreb.
 - September 25, 2015** The second OIKONET "Global Dwelling" conference takes place at the Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology. More than 50 delegates are attending this...

COMMENTS:

Orientation / Navigation:

For a majority of users, it was easy to find as long as the tile “Thinking Dwelling” was placed at the top of the home page. However, once it was not anymore at the top and people had to scroll the homepage to find it, they had a lot of difficulties in finding it. For many users **it was not clear that this program is considered as a Learning Space**, thus they did not look for it under the menu section “Learning Spaces”.

Sub-Page “Thinking Dwelling”:

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Latest Learning spaces

Learning spaces > THINKING DWELLING

THINKING_DWELLING is a program of activities –on-line and face-to-face- designed to engage students and teachers from different courses, levels and schools, in a joint process of reflection about contemporary dwelling. The activities to be submitted on-line (by students and teachers) are structured in three issues:

REPRESENTING: Dwelling as manifested through the arts- The object of this activity is to provide examples of ways of living through different art forms. For example, the relation of inhabitants and space expressed in a film scene, in a painting, in a passage of a literary work, in a sound...

EXPERIENCING: Personal ways of living- The purpose of this activity is to depict our own relationships with the spaces we live in, using any form of representation: a drawing, a video, a photograph, a text, a sound, in any combination.

PROJECTING: The forms of living- This activity has to do with collecting personal experiences about renowned houses we have had the opportunity to visit or even to live in. It consists of selecting a photograph of the house and projecting on it the life of their –real or ideal–inhabitants.

THINKING DWELLING

RELATED ITEMS

- Dissemination:**
 - Exhibition "Global Dwelling", Valencia
 - Exhibition Poster exhibition "Global Dwelling", Barcelona
- Images:**
 - Image Thinking Dwelling
- Partners:**
 - La Salle Architecture Engineering School
- Webs:**
 - Thinking Dwelling

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- Manchester International Conference

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RECENT NEWS

December 18, 2015 The fifth meeting of the subnetwork "Community Participation" is hosted by the Department of Architecture of the Ss. Cyril and

Users have the impression that there is **no real introduction to the program**. There is no title and no structure / hierarchy in the description. Users **expected the image “Thinking Dwelling” to be a link** to further information on the program (e.g. link to the website of the program).

The **links under “related items”** are **hardly visible to the user** (you need to scroll down on most screens to see the links). Especially the link to further information on the program should be easily visible (4). Some users wondered why it is necessary to have a sub-page on the OIKONET website and a separate website for the program: couldn’t one be eliminated to reduce the number of steps one has to do to reach the final information?

Thinking Dwelling Website:

It is not easy to get to the Thinking Dwelling Program from the OIKONET Website. Also from this website it is not clear to some users what the program is actually about. Under the menu “Activities” it shows pictures of students but it is not clear what activities they actually do (at least for outsiders). Under the menu “Programs” it only mentions past events and not future ones.

T2: SEARCH THE TERM “GENTRIFICATION” IN THE “OIKOPEDIA

Note: For the Eye-Tracking Test this task had to be split into two sub-tasks:

- T2.1 Go to OIKOPEDIA
- T2.2 In the OIKOPEDIA search the term “Gentrification”

Average satisfaction: **3.26**

Respondents: 34 + 5 = **39**

Task **not** completed by: **1**

Task completed with help: **1**

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Friday 23 September 2016
Manchester, UK

[OIKONET](#) [UCLan](#)

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November 18, 2015

The fifth meeting of the subnetwork "Housing Research" will take place in Zagreb, on November 20, 2015

September 09, 2015

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- Case repository
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RECENT NEWS

COMMENTS:

Orientation / Accessibility:

The link to the OIKOPEDIA is difficult to find. Many users did not look for it in the vertical lateral menu but would have expected to be able to access it from the main horizontal menu for example from the section "Outcomes". In fact, OIKOPEDIA is described there (D2.2 OIKOPEDIA entries) but there is no link leading to the OIKOPEDIA itself (should be added under "related items").

Readability:

The Link leading to the OIKOPEDIA in the lateral menu has a grey **font colour** on a **yellow/green background**. This, together with the very **small font size** makes the links very difficult to read, especially on small screens.

OIKOPEDIA:

As the number of entries are still limited, it is easy to find a concept such as gentrification on the left-hand list. However, if there are more entries, a search function might be useful to easily and quickly find the desired terms.

T3: SEARCH INFO ABOUT THE OUTCOMES OF THE PARTICIPATORY ACTION IN RIMINI (SPECIFICALLY A VIDEO)

Average satisfaction: **3.36**
 Respondents: 34 + 5 = **39**
 Task **not** completed by: **5**
 Task completed partially: 0

COMMENTS:

Orientation / Accessibility:

Users accessing the information from the main horizontal menu “Outcomes” → “Videos” → D3.2 Video... generally did not have any problem in finding and accessing the video. Some people did not see that there is a sub-menu (“Reports” / “Video”) and as “Reports” is selected by default, it became difficult for them to find the video. To accomplish this task a website **search function** would have been appreciated.

At the bottom of this sub-page it showed “Pages 1 2 3” even though there are only two videos and **pages 2 and 3 are empty**.

Some people tried to access the information from a tile on the home screen titled “Strategies for affordable housing in Rimini”. From there when you click on the “**Outcome**” Link in the text you arrive to the same place as from the menu “Outcomes” → “Videos” → D3.2 Video... . However, when **clicking on the title** you arrive to a separate page, which is under the menu section “Activities” with only an image of the video.

Home Project Consortium Partners Conferences Workshops **Activities** News Outcomes Meetings Learning spaces Newsletters Dissemination [CONTACT](#)

Latest activities

[Activities](#) > [Strategies for affordable housing in Rimini](#)

The **Outcome** about the participatory action carried out in Rimini, Italy is available.

RELATED ITEMS

 Images:
image_video_Rimini

[BACK TO ACTIVITIES](#)

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OIKONET Blogs

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- Community Participation
- Cottbus Workshop
- Housing Research Reader
- Lisbon Workshop
- Manchester International

By clicking on the image, people would expect some information instead of just a larger version of the image. When landing on this page, some users did not manage to find the video. To do so they actually had to click on the “Outcome” Link on the page to access the video. Some users thus feel that there are far too many steps to do to get to the video. **Advice:** Eliminate the sub-page under the menu section “Activities” and only keep the one under “Outcomes”. All links should then lead directly to this sub-page. This avoids confusion.

The same is true when trying to access the video from the **Oikonetwork**: There are different pages talking about the video in Rimini but not from all of them you can access the video:

- menu section “Activities” → “Participatory activity in Rimini, Italy- Update of the work in-progress”
- menu section “Deliverables” → “D3.2 Video reporting”
- menu section “Outcomes” → “D3.2 Video reporting of participatory actions: Strategies for affordable housing in Rimini”

Only from the page under the section “Outcomes” you can directly access the video. The many pages with different content create confusion in the users.

Some people tried to access the information through the OIKOPEDIA, where they managed to find information on the participatory action but did not manage to access the video (2) (if you access it from section Activities or Deliverables). Those accessing it from the section “Outcomes” find the video also on the OIKOPEDIA. This is confusing!

Video page:

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Latest videos

Videos > **D3.2 Video reporting of participatory actions: Strategies for affordable housing in Rimini**

Summary of the participatory action carried out in Rimini, Italy, to bring together local stakeholders in a process aimed at finding solutions to the shortage of affordable housing in the city.

RELATED ITEMS

- Deliverables:**
 - D3.2 Video reporting
- Partners:**
 - Heriscape - Heritage and Landscape, Training and Consulting
 - ORDINE ARCHITETTI PAESAGGISTI PIANIFICATORI e CONSERVATORI DELLA PROVINCIA DI RIMINI
- Videos:**
 - Video housing Rimini

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OIKONET Blogs

- Barcelona International**

The font size and spacing of the “related items” section is very small and thus difficult to read.

T4: SEARCH THE DESCRIPTION OF THE PARTICIPATORY ACTION IN BRATISLAVA IN THE BLOG "COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION".

Note: For the Eye-Tracking Test this task had to be split into two sub-tasks:

- **T4.1 Go to the Blog Community Participation**
- **T4.2 In the blog "Community Participation" search the description of the participatory action in Bratislava**

Average satisfaction: **3.63**

Respondents: 34 + 5 = 39

Task **not** completed by: **5**

Task completed with help: 0

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COMMENTS:

Orientation / Accessibility:

Most users managed to find and access the blog through the vertical navigation menu on the left.

Blog “Community Participation”:

Community participation

HOME PARTICIPATORY ACTIONS BARCELONA RIMINI BRATISLAVA SKOPIE

Barcelona Rimini

PARTICIPATORY ACTIONS

M E T f p G+ Recomendar esto en Google

No hay comentarios:

Publicar un comentario en la entrada

Introduce tu comentario...

Comentar como: Anna Picco (G) ▼

Publicar Vista previa Salir Avisarme

Contribuyentes

- Iub
- Heriscape
- OIKONETOL LLP
- Ognen Marina

Archivo del blog

- 2015 (4)
 - diciembre (1)
 - OIKONET Community participation workshop in Skopje...
 - marzo (1)
 - febrero (1)
 - enero (1)
- 2014 (11)
- 2013 (4)

Navigation: There are two navigation menus (main and secondary) with partly the same names. Two users could not find the “Bratislava” section: they only looked at the secondary menu.

Advice: Eliminate the secondary menu; its sections are already present in the main menu.

Content: Under the tab “Participatory Actions” users expect a description of what participatory actions are in general and a list of all participatory actions. As it is, this tab is not useful. Furthermore, it is not immediately clear that the city name tabs correspond to a singular participatory action.

Language: The blog’s built-in items are not in English but in Spanish. This creates confusion and is not coherent.

T5: SEARCH THE CONTACT OF THE LEADER OF WP2 (HOUSING RESEARCH)

Average satisfaction: **3.54**

Respondents: 34 + 5 = **39**

Task **not** completed by: **6**

Task completed with help: 1+2

COMMENTS:

Orientation / Accessibility:

Most users managed to find the contact person quickly and without any difficulties. The contact link is placed well visible in the upper right-hand corner, where one would expect it. However, one person suggested to outline the link more to make it more visible (larger font-size). Those who did not complete the task, either did not find the link “contact” or expected to find only a general e-mail address under this link, and thus focused their research without success on all other areas of the website (mainly Project and Consortium Tab) (6).

Readability:

Users **liked this page as there is not too much text on the page**, which makes a nice change from the rest of the website.

T6: GO TO THE OIKONET FACEBOOK PAGE AND SEARCH FOR INFOS ABOUT THE "HOUSING DESIGN" MOOC: IS IT STILL RUNNING? WHEN WILL IT FINISH? CAN I STILL ENROLL?

Average satisfaction: **2.03**

Respondents: 33 + 0 = **33**

Task **not** completed by: **17**

Task completed with help: 1

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COMMENTS:

Orientation / Accessibility:

Most people **managed to find and access the Facebook page without problems** (6). However, **finding information on the MOOC was very difficult, because** the news was not anymore at the top of the page when a majority of partners did the usability test. In fact, searching Facebook pages for information is difficult, as they are structured by timeline and not by theme, and there is no search tool (12). The low satisfaction and success score might be mainly due to this difficulty. When the usability test was presented to the project partners, the MOOC was the first entry of the Facebook page, thus very easy to find. However, as many

partners did the tests only many weeks later, the MOOC entry moved down and was not any more visible among the latest posts.

The screenshot shows the Facebook page for OIKONET. The page header includes the name 'OIKONET', a search bar, and navigation options like 'Page', 'Messages', 'Notifications', 'Insights', and 'Publishing Tools'. The cover photo features a blue background with a white silhouette of a city skyline and the text 'A global multidisciplinary network on housing research and learning.' The profile picture is a circular logo with five colored segments (red, green, blue, yellow, purple). The main content area shows a post from Annina Picco Schwendener, dated December 18, 2015, at 11:48pm. The post is a link share for a conference announcement. The announcement text reads: 'THIRD OIKONET CONFERENCE HAS BEEN ANNOUNCED. The third OIKONET International Conference on Global Dwelling has been announced. The conference will take place in Manchester, on...'. The OIKONET.ORG logo is visible at the bottom of the announcement. On the right side of the page, there is a 'Promote' section showing 'THIS WEEK' statistics: 28 Post Reach, 21 Post Engagement, and 0 Website Clicks. Below this is a 'Recent' section with years 2015 and 2014. At the bottom right, there is a 'See Your Ad Here' section with a small advertisement for the conference and a 'Boost Post' button.

T7: SEARCH INFOS ABOUT THE LEARNING SPACE "THRESHOLD MATTERS": IS IT STILL ACTIVE? WHICH ARE THE PARTNERS INVOLVED?

Average satisfaction: **3.66**

Respondents: 33 + 5 = **38**

Task **not** completed by: **0**

Task completed with help: **1**

COMMENTS:

Orientation / Accessibility:

For most users it was **easy to find the Learning Space under the menu section “Learning spaces”**.

Sub-page THRESHOLD MATTERS:

It is not clear what the icon “w” stands for. One user thought it would lead directly to the workspace. The icon stands for OIKONETWORK, but this **should be explained somewhere**.

Learning space “THRESHOLD MATTERS” page:

Structure / Design: Users did not like the structure / design of the page. It does not look inviting and does not inspire users to read through the content. It looks chaotic and is very different from the OIKONET pages.

Orientation: Finding the requested information on the LS was difficult. As the calendar of the

workspace is not active, it is difficult to understand whether the LS is still active or not. (10)

Navigation: There is no link from the Workspace page back to the OIKONET page. Only the OIKODOMOS website is mentioned at the bottom of the Learning Space page.

Naming ambiguity: “Learning Spaces” or “Workspaces”? Are they the same? Users get confused (2). The difference and the reason why both terms are used should be explained somewhere.

T8: SEARCH THE VIDEO OF THE KEYNOTE SPEECH OF EKIM TAN AT THE BARCELONA CONFERENCE

Average satisfaction: **4.13**

Respondents: 33 + 5 = 38

Task **not** completed by: **4**

Task completed with help: **1**

The screenshot shows the OIKONET website interface. The top navigation bar includes 'Home', 'Project', 'Consortium', 'Partners', 'Conferences', 'Workshops', 'Activities', 'News', 'Outcomes', 'Meetings', 'Learning spaces', 'Newsletters', 'Dissemination', and 'CONTACT'. The 'Conferences' menu is highlighted with a red box. Below it, the 'Barcelona' sub-menu is also highlighted with a red box. The main content area displays the details for the Barcelona International Conference, including a description, a list of participants, and a 'KEYNOTE SPEECH' section. The keynote speech by Ekim Tan is highlighted with a red box, and the 'Video recording' link is also highlighted with a red box. The right sidebar contains social media links, a newsletter subscription form, and sections for 'OIKONETWORK', 'OIKONET Blogs', 'OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus', and 'RECENT NEWS'.

COMMENTS:

Orientation / Accessibility:

For a majority of users this task was **easy to accomplished** (9). For some of the users it was not immediately clear that there is a sub-menu with the names of the conference, and thus they got stuck within the “Bratislava” conference, which is selected by default.

Users liked the breakdown of the page in conference sessions in order to support orientation.

Readability:

Users liked the **good contrast between font and background colour** on this page. However, some users had difficulty in reading the texts because of the **small font-sizes**.

T9: GO TO THE OIKONETWORK

Average satisfaction: **4.55**

Respondents: 33 + 5 = **38**

Task **not** completed by: **2**

Task completed with help: **0**

COMMENTS:

Orientation / Accessibility:

For most users this task was easy to accomplish (8). However, some of them had difficulties in finding the link, as one tends to overlook the vertical menu on the right. On smaller screens you have to scroll down / right to visualize the information.

Readability:

Font of the link is very small. There is not enough contrast between the Oikonetwork description font colour and the background colour. This makes it difficult to read.

T10: WITHIN THE OIKONETWORK SEARCH THE DOCUMENT PRESENTING THE INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP HELD IN COTTBUS LAST JUNE

Average satisfaction: 3.76

Respondents: 33 + 4 = 37

Task **not** completed by: 2

Task completed with help: 1

COMMENTS:

Oikonetwork:

It has a funny design, which looks good, and works well only if there are few information nodes. With more nodes the text overlays and becomes unreadable. Generally, also here diagrams and fonts are too small to be well readable. When the graphs open, they keep moving for a while, which makes it hard to click on an item.

When one clicks on the “Information” item, no additional information is displayed on the workshop (as expected) but only a link to a website.

Users had to be guided into the Oikonetwork by the experts in order to understand how it works. There should be an explanation on how to use it at the beginning together with a description of what it is and what it is useful for. For example, it is very difficult to guess that at the top you can click on the different voices so that the related items in the graph disappear (which is actually very helpful to better read the graph).

T11: WITHIN OIKONETWORK LOOK FOR THE NEWS RELATED TO WP2 (HOUSING RESEARCH)

Average satisfaction: 3.30

Respondents: 32 + 5 = 37

Task **not** completed by: 1

Task completed with help: 1

The screenshot shows the OIKONETWORK digital platform interface. The 'Workpackages' menu item is highlighted with a red box. The main content area displays a semantic map for 'WP2 HOUSING RESEARCH'. The map is a complex network of nodes and lines, with a central node labeled 'WP2 HOUSING RESEARCH'. The nodes are small icons with text labels, representing various research topics and activities related to housing research. The map is difficult to read due to its complexity and small font size.

COMMENTS:

Oikonetwork: Again, users would have appreciated an introduction explaining how the OIKONETWORK works.

Readability: The news are difficult to find and hard to read. Users referred to the graph as: “Then this large spider web appears where absolutely nothing is readable” or “what is the point of this “Supernova”-style?” The diagrams and fonts are too small and the colours are too light. The grey font colour of the text makes it hard to distinguish whether an item is selected or not.

Predictability: When clicking on the items’ names at the top, the related items in the graph disappear: this is the opposite of what a user would expect. Expected behaviour is: clicking on “News” would hide everything except news.

However, some users liked the idea of the map and the interactivity the semantic map is offering. Navigation: For several users the first try was the menu option “News”. However,

from there it is not clear which news are related to WP2.

Loading Time: While doing the Eye-Tracking tests, the semantic network of WP2 took very long to load.

T12: WITHIN OIKONETWORK LOOK FOR INFORMATION ON RESEARCH ACTIVITIES ON "RESETTLEMENT": WHO IS WORKING ON IT? WHICH OTHER THEMES / SUBTHEMES ARE CONNECTED TO IT?

Average satisfaction: 3.42
 Respondents: 33 + 5 = 38
 Task **not** completed by: 2
 Task completed with help: 0

COMMENTS:

Oikonetwork:

Navigation: For several users it was not clear whether to choose the menu option “Activities” or “Research Issues”. This might be due to the wording of the question.

Predictability: When the menu option “Activities” or “Research Issues” are selected a **white page appears**. This is a bit confusing. It would be useful to have some introductory text (what can you find under “Activities” or under “Research Issues”) or at least some instructions on

how to proceed like “choose a term from the list on the left-hand side”.

Orientation: Terms are **ordered alphabetically**, which allows to find them easily. However, a **search field** would still be useful, especially when having very long lists.

T13: GO BACK TO THE OIKONET WEBSITE AND SEARCH THE LAST ISSUE OF THE NEWSLETTER (IF S/HE WANTS S/HE CAN SUBSCRIBE TO IT)

Average satisfaction: **4.62**

Respondents: 32 + 5

Task **not** completed by: **0**

Task completed with help: 0

COMMENTS:

Orientation / Accessibility:

The newsletters are **easy to find and to subscribe to** for most users. However, some users had difficulties in finding the subscription option within the newsletter page. It is not very well visible. When subscribing to the Newsletter you **do not get any feedback message**. The user is unsure whether the subscription has been completed or not.

Newsletter:

Design: The newsletter itself is **well formatted and clear**. There is not too much text in it and gives just enough information. Only the “welcome” message at the beginning of the newsletter could use larger line spacing.

EYE-TRACKING ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The usability test with the eye-tracking tool was done by five collaborators at USI. The eye-tracking tool allows to follow the eye-movement of the testers, thus understanding what they are looking at while doing a task. The analysis of the Eye-Tracking data focused on some specific aspects, which were considered particularly relevant to the usability analysis of the web-portal.

A major point of interest is, for example, how users look at and navigate the home page. Furthermore, an analysis has been done on how users were looking for the OIKOPEDIA Link and the Oikonetwork link, two important resources created by the project.

NAVIGATION OF HOMEPAGE:

The home page is the entry point of each website. It should be the point that offers easy access to all other contents. It is thus particularly important to understand how the users look at it, what they see and what they oversee. The following graph from the Eye-Tracking software (Gaze Plot) shows the sum of all the eye movements done by the five testers whenever they were on the homepage during the whole test (all visits made to the home page during all tasks). Each user is represented by a different colour and each bubble is numbered indicating the sequence of the eye-movements. The bigger the bubble is, the longer the user fixed that specific point.

The graph shows clearly that the area covered by the main horizontal navigation menu is the area where testers mostly looked at while doing their tasks. It also shows that many users do not look at the lower part of the lateral vertical menu. This explains why for several people it was very difficult to find the links and topics that were not present in the main horizontal menu. The following two graphs show the same information just in a different way. The first one is a heat map. The redder the area is; the more eye-fixations it has registered. Again, it shows that the horizontal menu is the hottest zone of the homepage. While the upper area of the vertical menu still registered some eye-movements, the lower part registered hardly any. The second graph shows three cluster areas. The green cluster is the one where most eye fixations were registered, whereas the red one only had very few ones.

LOOKING FOR OIKOPEDIA LINK:

Testers had difficulties in accessing the OIKOPEDIA link and would have expected it to be accessible also from the main horizontal menu. This results also from the Eye-Tracking tests. The Eye-Tracking software allows defining an area of interest (AOI), which in this case was the area of the link (see image below).

At this point, the software is able to calculate the time from the start of the task until the eye first gets to the AOI (Time to First Fixation). Furthermore, it is able to tell how many fixations (on other areas) the tester did before s/he first fixes the AOI (Fixations Before). It is also able to tell, how many times the testers looked at the AOI during the whole task (Fixation Count) and how long it took until they first clicked on the AOI (Time to first mouse click), thus finishing the task.

The graph below shows this data for the five testers. Tester Asta has no indication of “time to first mouse click” because she never clicked on the link. However, we know from the test monitoring that she found the link and that it took her 151.98 seconds to do so. This information was added manually to the table below.

Time to First Fixation The time from the start of the stimulus display until the test participant fixates on the AOI or AOI Group for the first time (seconds).

Fixations Before Number of times the participant fixates on the media before fixating on an AOI or AOI Group for the first time (count).

Fixation Count Number of times the participant fixates on an AOI or an AOI Group (count).

Time to First Mouse Click The time in seconds until the first click is made within an AOI or AOI Group.

Mouse Click Count Number of times the participant clicked inside an AOI or an AOI Group (count).

Recordings	Time to First Fix...		Fixations Before		Fixation Count		Time to First Mo...		Mouse Click Count	
	All Media		All Media		All Media		All Media		All Media	
	oikopedia		oikopedia		oikopedia		oikopedia		oikopedia	
	N (Count)	Sum (.Seconds)	N (Count)	Sum (Count)	N (Count)	Sum (Count)	N (Count)	Sum (.Seconds)	N (Count)	Sum (Count)
Asta	1	36,47	1	137,00	1	4,00	-	151,98	-	-
Elena	1	98,36	1	361,00	1	9,00	1	102,90	1	1,00
Elisabetta	1	14,25	1	60,00	1	5,00	1	16,85	1	1,00
JingJing	1	158,58	1	472,00	1	4,00	1	159,27	1	1,00
Silvia	1	34,34	1	109,00	1	3,00	1	129,60	1	1,00
All Recordings	5	342,00	5	1139,00	5	25,00	4	408,62	4	4,00

From the following table, we can see that testers Asta and Silvia actually fixed the AOI (=link) after a bit more than 30 seconds; however, they did not understand that that was the area they were looking for, because only more than 1.5 minutes later they actually clicked on it. This confirms what already emerged from the other user tests: that the link is not well visible, that it does not stand out, so even if people actually overflowed it with their eyes they did not recognize it. In part, this is due to the very small font used.

Only one tester (Elisabetta) found the link and clicked on it after a short time (16.85 sec). All the others employed between 1.5 and 2.5 minutes to recognize the AOI as the link to click. They did many fixations beforehand, meaning that they were looking for the link in other places. The video of the single eye-tracks for the tasks shows that most testers were looking for the information first on the main horizontal menu.

LOOKING FOR OIKONETWORK LINK:

The first image below shows the eye movements of all five testers during task number 9 (= looking for the Oikonetwork link). It shows that not many eye-fixations were needed in order to find the link. This is in line with the fact that the testers found the link quite easily, in part due to the fact that by now (this was task number 9) the testers got acquainted with the website and its structure, and in part because the link is placed in the upper part of the vertical lateral menu. However, from both the gaze plot and the heat map it is visible that some testers were first looking for the link in the main horizontal menu.

CONCLUSIONS: GENERAL ISSUES THAT EMERGED ON THE WEBSITE

In this concluding section, the main general issues that emerged during the usability analysis are summarized:

Homepage (HP):

- It is **overwhelming**. There is **too much text** and **content** on the homepage (6), and the **font is too small** to read it well (especially when reading it on smaller monitors). This does not inspire people to read contents and thus they tend to look only at the horizontal menu and not at the content and right hand menu
- **Content / Structure:**
 - o There is **no clear structure** and is **confusing** (2)
 - o Users would expect an **introduction to the project** and some explanation on how the website is structured (where can I find what, how many menus are there, ...); the introduction should include **a selling point** (why should I look at this webpage? Why is it interesting for me?)
 - o It only **contains project activities** (each tile is an activity) → you can find exactly the same information in the menu section “Activities”. Many of these activities are again mentioned in the section “recent news” on the right-hand menu of the homepage (duplicate information)
 - o Most sub-pages (e.g. Activities or Outcomes) are structured as News Feed, which is a bit strange. The webpage seems a large archive like this

Navigation:

- **Horizontal Menu** on the top:
 - o Each menu section / page should have at least two lines of introduction (what can I find in this section, ...)
 - o **1st level menu:**
 - It is not well visible: **text font is very small** and the colour is grey (5)

- There are far **too many menu options** (4): some options might be merged, like:
 - Merge “Conferences”, “Workshops”, “Meetings” into an “Events” section
 - Merge “Activities” & “News”, they are similar
 - Merge “Partners” & “Consortium”
- Create drop-down sub-menu lists (instead of 2nd level menu)
- **2nd level menu:**
 - Many users oversee it when inside a menu section such as “Outcomes” or “Dissemination” and look only at the content of the already selected sub-menu
 - It is confusing that on the HP, the 1st and 2nd level menus are divided by a banner.
- **Vertical Menu on the right:**
 - The lateral menu was understood as an active part of the home page and not as menu. For this reason, many users oversee the menu options when looking for content.
 - The menu options are difficult to read due to their small font-size and the colours. A grey font is difficult to read on a yellow/green background.
- **Search option:**
 - In the whole website there is no search option, which makes it very difficult to find specific information, especially if you are not familiar with the project’s structure (10).

Target audience / Involvement:

- It is **not clear to whom the website is addressed**. Who should be its users? (3). You have to know the vocabulary / terminology of the project in order not to get lost within the website.
- **"Call of actions" are missing** (e.g. "be part of", "participate in conference"). The website seems more an **archive** of past activities. This does not incentive external people to participate in the network.

Remarks on the website as a whole:

- There is a lot of focus on "network" but you **cannot see any people on the website**.
- **Important content does not stand out** to be spotted.
- **Section “Project”**: when clicking on the large image / graph, users would expect it to lead to some more in-depth information on the project (project leaders, ...).

Visual appeal / Layout:

- The **look & feel** of the website is **pleasant**.
- When loading in IE, the website always loads as if it has a **grey curtain**. Only by clicking on some content the fonts get really black and the backgrounds clearer (by Anna Picco)